

CREEP AND CREEP RUPTURE OF STITCHED COMPOSITES

Feiyi Pang¹, C. H. Wang² and R. G. Bathgate¹

¹ *School of Engineering and Technology, Deakin University, Geelong, Australia*

² *Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory, Melbourne, Australia*

SUMMARY: Plain woven composites have been found to exhibit significant creep at ambient temperature with low to medium stress levels. One effective means to improve the creep resistance of woven composites is to introduce through-thickness stitching. Experiments were conducted using specimens stitched with different threads at various densities prior to resin injection. The results showed that stitching can significantly reduce delamination and hence enhance creep resistance, provided the stitches are aligned in the direction of loading. The effectiveness of stitching was found to increase with stitch density and thread modulus.

KEYWORDS: creep, creep testing, creep rupture, temperature creep, tensile testing, woven composite, stitched composite, fibers

INTRODUCTION

Woven composite materials are extensively used in a wide range of applications, including aerospace structures, infrastructures, etc, and frequently these structures are designed to carry static and fatigue loads. Due to the presence of a viscous matrix, e.g., epoxy, and the architecture of these materials, woven composites may exhibit significant creep as a function of stress, temperature and time [1,2,3,4]. Furthermore, the ultimate failure loads may also depend on the time period over which the load is applied. While metallic components normally have negligible creep at ambient temperature, creep and creep rupture are of great importance in the design and application of composites with a viscous phase which has a low glass transition temperature. Engineering designs, based on static properties without considering time dependent degradation of composite materials may lead to and eventually cause catastrophic disasters, especially when the design load is high when compared with the failure strength. In this regard, creep rupture of composites is a serious concern.

Since real time experimental testing and evaluation of the creep behaviour of large scale structures is very difficult and time consuming, considerable efforts have been devoted to the characterisation of creep using analytical or semi-empirical approaches. Earlier attempts include a power law constitutive relation by Norton [5]. Lilholt [6] showed the creep of off-axis unidirectional composites, can be predicted by using the law of mixture, taking into account the different creep properties of the constituents. These studies, however, have so far been concerned mainly with extensional creep of various fiber lay-up angles [7], or randomly oriented fiber composite [8]. Very little is known about the creep and creep rupture behaviours of woven composites, with or without stitching.

The objective of this paper is to present an experimental study of the creep rupture behaviour of woven composites at ambient temperatures. Through-thickness stitching was investigated as a promising means of improving the creep resistance of composites.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

A two-dimensional woven fiber composite was manufactured using a standard resin injection technique. Five layers of bi-directional carbon fibre cloth were placed in between two layers of glass fibre fabric which was bi-directional E-glass cloth (top and bottom). The fabric was stitched through the thickness to obtain the preform, using a modified lock stitching method [2,3,4]. When the stitching process was completed, a standard resin injection procedure was applied to obtain the stitched composite. The resin used was Epocast 50-A, mixed with hardener 946 at a ratio of 100:15 by weight. Finally the composite was cured three days at room temperature followed by a post curing process of 2 hours at 80°C. The resulting composites had a volume fraction of approximately 0.5, half of which was aligned parallel to the axis of the specimens and the rest aligned perpendicular to the specimen axis. Table 1 shows the specifications of cotton and carbon threads used in the present work.

Table 1: Characterisation of stitch yarn

	cotton yarn (Tex=300)	carbon yarn (Tex=200)	thick carbon (Tex=800)
Tensile strength (MPa)	350	3400	3400
Modulus(GPa)	2.857	238	238

The stitching process was repeated along the loading direction as shown in Fig.1. The manual stitching process was achieved with a high level of control and repeatability to provide evenly distributed stitch points throughout the hybrid fabric preform.

Tensile Static and Creep Testing

The size of the specimen was 200mm long, 15 mm wide and 1.5 mm thick. The two stitching lines were symmetry to the centre. At each end, 50mm of the specimen was held in the grips, leaving a test area of 100mm long and 15mm wide.

Fig.1 (a) Lock stitching pattern and (b) loading direction.

Static tensile tests were conducted to quantify the mechanical properties of the unstitched and stitched woven composites, with particular attention to the effect of stitching on the in-plane tensile strength and elastic modulus. As shown in Table 2, both the Young's Modulus and the tensile strength increased as a result of stitching, suggesting that stitching of the preforms did not result in any loss of in-plane stiffness and strength. Tensile creep tests were conducted using a workshop constructed lever arm system. Constant load was applied to each specimen, corresponding stress levels ranging from 10% to 90% of the respective tensile strength. At least two specimens were tested at each condition to assess the variations between specimens.

Table 2: Mechanical properties of non-stitch and stitched. Stitch threads and density

Static Properties	non-stitch composite	Stitched			
		cotton pitch=5mm	cotton pitch=10mm	carbon pitch=5mm	carbon pitch=10mm
Tensile strength (MPa)	279	309	297.5	340	333
Elastic Modulus (GPa)	53.5	59.1	51.6	78.1	73.2

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Stitch Threads and Density

The experimental creep curves for specimens without stitch are shown in Figure 2(a), where the creep strains measured at various constant applied stress are plotted against time. Here the strains are the total longitudinal strain, ϵ , recorded using an extensometer. It is clear that very little creep occurred at stress level equal to or below 50 MPa, roughly one fifth of the ultimate tensile strength of the unstitched specimens.

Fig.2(b) shows the creep behaviour of specimens stitched with cotton threads at a pitch=5mm along the loading direction. Comparison with the unstitched specimens reveals that higher stress was required to induce the same amount of creep at a given time. The creep response of high density (pitch=5mm) carbon thread stitched composites are shown in Fig.2(c). As comparing with the cotton thread stitched composites (same pitch) even more reduction in the creep strain at a given stress level was observed. To further examine the influence of thread stiffness on creep, experiments have also been carried out for specimens stitched with a thicker carbon thread. The results are shown in Fig.2(d).

For a given stitching thread, the density of stitching was also important, as evidenced in Fig.3(a) and (b). The experimental results showed that the smaller the stitch pitch, the more effective was the stitching. The different creep behaviours of unstitched and stitched composites can be better seen in Fig.4, where the specimens were tested at an identical stress level. It is evident that for the same pitch, thick carbon thread was clearly the most effective in terms of reducing creep.

Fig.2: Creep responses of (a) unstitched composite (b) cotton

(c) carbon (d) thick carbon composite

Fig.3: Effects of stitching density on creep behaviour (a) cotton thread (205MPa) (b) carbon thread (MPa).

Fig.4: Effects of stitching and type of stitch fiber on creep behaviour (205MPa)

Fig.5: Variation of the creep rate for different stress levels

The relationships between the creep rate and the stress are shown in Fig.5. It was found that the creep rate increased nearly linearly with increase of stress at low and medium stress levels. This suggested that the unstitched and stitched woven composites could be considered as linear viscoelastic materials. An accurate description for stitched and unstitched composites can be obtained by using linear viscoelastic theory. In the present the four-element, Burger's model was adopted to characterise the creep behaviour. The total strain at time t is equal to the sum of the following strains:

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \tag{1}$$

The relationship between σ and ε for Burger's model were considered as[9]:

$$\sigma + \left(\frac{\eta_1}{R_1} + \frac{\eta_1}{R_2} + \frac{\eta_2}{R_3} \right) \dot{\sigma} + \frac{\eta_1 \eta_2}{R_1 R_2} \ddot{\sigma} = \eta_1 \dot{\varepsilon} + \frac{\eta_1 \eta_2}{R_2} \ddot{\varepsilon} \tag{2}$$

Fig.6: Burgers Model

The predictions of Burger's model are compared with the experimental results obtained at ambient temperatures, and, as shown in Fig.2, the correlation was very good. It was found that good agreement between theory and experiment was illustrated for the linear viscoelastic response characterised. The error in both estimates was approximately 4%. The accuracy of Burger's model has been illustrated for such materials [9]. The results of the present investigation indicate that Burger's model has the potential to accurately predict the linear viscoelastic response of stitched and unstitched woven composites.

Creep Rupture

The experimental results obtained for stage I and II regions represent the behaviour that would occur under service conditions with low to medium applied stresses. As the applied stress increases, failure in the form of creep rupture may result, even at ambient temperature. If composite materials are to be used reliably for extended periods of time, it is important to know not only how much the material deforms but if and when the material will fail. To this end, experiments were carried out by increasing the applied stress level to between 85% and 95% of the tensile strength. The results for unstitched, cotton stitched, carbon stitched and thick carbon stitched are shown in Fig.7(a)-(d). Compared with un-stitched composite under the same stress level, stitched specimens generally took longer to fail. The creep curves for all specimens appeared to be rather similar, exhibiting some stage III creep prior to rupture. A comparison of specimens stitched with different threads is shown in Fig.8, clearly demonstrating the effectiveness of stitching to increase creep rupture stress level for a given time or increasing creep rupture life for a given stress level.

Fig.7: Rupture behaviour of
(a) unstitched composite

(b) cotton stitched composite

It can also be observed that the creep strain at failure, as shown in Figs.7(a)-(d), decreases as the applied stress increases, indicating a gradual transition towards a more brittle behaviour. It has been suggested that the creep lifetime of many materials can be correlated using a Monkman-Grant (see e.g., Service [10]) type of relationship which relates the failure time t_f to the creep rate $\dot{\epsilon}$

$$t_f = C \dot{\epsilon}^{-m} \tag{3}$$

Where C and m are material and environmental constants. An exponent of $m=1$ implies a constant strain at failure and assumes that creep in the primary and tertiary stages is negligible, whereas an exponent greater than unity means that the failure strain should increase as the strain rate decreases. The failure creep strain for unstitched and stitched specimens are plotted versus the failure time in Fig.9. The creep rates for the unstitched and stitched composites are shown in Fig.10 against the time to failure, at two different temperatures. It can be seen that there exists a universal relationship between the creep strain rate and the time to failure, thus providing a creep rupture criterion that can be identified relatively easily, as C , m are independent of temperature, stitching method and stitching density.

For practical application purpose, a relationship that gives the time to failure for any given applied stress and temperature would be more useful. Since the results of this study have shown that for a given creep strain rate the time to failure is independent of the temperature and stitching, Norton law and (3) can be combined to provide an expression that gives the time to failure as a function of the applied stress:

$$t_f = CA^{-m} \sigma_a^{-mn} \tag{4}$$

Fig. 7(c) carbon stitched composite Fig. 7(d) thick carbon stitched composite.

Where C and m are constants, independent of geometry and temperature, A and n are dependent on temperature and stitching threads and pitch.

Fig.8: Effects of stitching and type of stitch stitched composite.

Fig.9: Creep failure strain as a function of failure time.

Fig.10: Master rupture curves for woven and stitched composites

CONCLUSION

1. Stitching, with the stitches being parallel to the dominant loading direction, has been found to be very effective in slowing down creep the process and enhancing creep rupture strength.
2. Under uniaxial tension, unstitched composites would fail due to creep rupture at stress levels less than 80% of the static tensile strength and ambient temperature within a relatively short period of time.
3. The density of stitching also plays an important role, as the smaller the stitch pitch, the more effective is the stitching
4. The application of Burger's model was adopted in this investigation to predict the creep response of stitched and unstitched woven composites.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Authors are grateful to Mr. G. Giles for assistance in constructing the testing facilities.

REFERENCES

1. Shen, S. Z., "Prediction of long-term behaviour of fibre reinforced plastic", *In proceedings of the international Conference on Composite Materials*, Vol. 2, Guangzhou, China, 1989, pp. 1-5.
2. Pang, F., Wang, C. H. and Bathgate, R. G., "A creep study on stitched fiber/resin composite", *proceedings of 1st Australasian Congress on Applied Mechanics*, Institution of Engineers Australia, 1996, pp:357-361.

3. Pang, F., Wang, C. H. and Bathgate, R. G., "Creep response of woven fiber composites: effect of stitching", accepted by *Composite Science and Technology*.
4. Pang, F., Wang, C. H. and Bathgate, R. G., "Effects of stitch thread and density on the creep behaviour of woven composites", submitted to *Journal of Composite Materials*.
5. Norton, F. H., "The creep of steel at high temperature", *New york : McGrawHill*. 1929.
6. Lilholt, H., "Models for creep of fibrous composite materials", *Materials Forum*. Vol.11, 1988, pp. 133-139.
7. Chung I., Sun C. T. & Chang I. Y., "Modelling creep in thermoplastic Composites", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 27, No. 10, 1993, pp. 1009-1029.
8. Wang Y. R. & Chou T. W., "Analytical modelling of creep behaviour of short fibre reinforced ceramic matrix composites", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No. 9, 1992, pp.1269-1287.
9. Findley W. N., Lai J. S. & Onaran K., "Creep and relaxation of nonlinear viscoelastic materials", *North-Holland Publishing Company*.
10. Service T. H., "Creep rupture of a phenolic-alumina particulate composite", *Journal of Materials Science* 28, 1993, pp : 6087-6090.